

ASHVIN USE CASES FOR DIGITAL TWIN IN BUILDING AND MAINTENANCE

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ASHVIN has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 958161. This document reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Project Title	Assistants for Healthy, Safe, and Productive Virtual Construction Design, Operation & Maintenance using a Digital Twin
Project Acronym	ASHVIN
Grant Agreement No	958161
Instrument	Research & Innovation Action
Topic	LC-EEB-08-2020 - Digital Building Twins
Start Date of Project	1st October 2020
Duration of Project	42 Months

Name of the publication	ASHVIN Digital Twin Use Cases
Dissemination level	PU
Task leader/Main author	Technical University of Berlin (TUB)
Contributing partners	ALL
Reviewer(s)	AUS

ABSTRACT

This document gathers the 10 use cases defined for the digital twin tools developed and demonstrated under the ASHVIN research project. The use cases enable the capture, specification and exchange of best practices and make them accessible to the entire built asset industry.

KEYWORDS

Digital Twin, Building Information Modelling, Impact, Planning, Use Case Models, Demonstration, BuildingSmart, Design and engineering, construction, maintenance

REVISIONS

Version	Submission date	Comments	Author
V0.1	02/04/2024	Publication	The ASHVIN team

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ASHVIN PROJECT

ASHVIN aims at enabling the European construction industry to significantly improve its productivity, while reducing cost and ensuring absolutely safe work conditions, by providing a proposal for a European wide digital twin standard, an open-source digital twin platform integrating IoT and image technologies, and a set of tools and demonstrated procedures to apply the platform and the standard proven to guarantee specified productivity, cost, and safety improvements. The envisioned platform will provide a digital representation of the construction product at hand and allow to collect real-time digital data before, during, and after production of the product to continuously monitor changes in the environment and within the production process. Based on the platform, ASHVIN will develop and demonstrate applications that use the digital twin data. These applications will allow it to fully leverage the potential of the IoT based digital twin platform to reach the expected impacts (better scheduling forecast by 20%; better allocation of resources and optimization of equipment usage; reduced number of accidents; reduction of construction projects). The ASHVIN solutions will overcome worker protection and privacy issues that come with the tracking of construction activities, provide means to fuse video data and sensor data, integrate geo-monitoring data, provide multi-physics simulation methods for digital representing the behavior of a product (not only its shape), provide evidence based engineering methods to design for productivity and safety, provide 4D simulation and visualization methods of construction processes, and develop a lean planning process supported by real-time data. All innovations will be demonstrated on real-world construction projects across Europe. The ASHVIN consortium combines strong R&I players from 9 EU member states with strong expertise in construction and engineering management, digital twin technology, IoT, and data security / privacy.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The ASHVIN project, which ran for 42 months until March 2024, developed a novel digital twin solution supporting the construction and asset management sectors to become more productive, safe, and efficient. The project gathered 15 partners across Europe to develop the solution and pilot it in 10 different pilot sites, which enabled the created system to attend the technology readiness level (TRL1) 6 (E.G., the technology was demonstrated in a relevant environment). Now, based on the technical achievements and research on the demonstration sites, the project drafted a set of use cases to communicate the abilities of the created digital twin solution and contribute to the general uptake of digital twin technologies in the construction sector.

It is important to share the context around the use cases before sharing them. The next subsections present the ASHVIN system behind the use cases and the methodology used to draft them.

1.1 Basis for the ASHVIN Use Cases

The research and innovation work were done in the project's several work packages, including:

- **WP1 IoT driven digital twin platform** that focused on building an industrial open-source, secure, and highly scalable digital twin platform that is fully IoT enabled.
- **WP2 Design for productivity and safety** that developed possibilities to allow designers and engineers to account for the aspects of productivity, resource efficiency, and safety early in the design phase, allowing for the use of digital twin technology at the start of the product development lifecycle.
- **WP3 Data fusion for real-time construction monitoring** that established novel algorithms for extracting the required features to be mapped from the real world to the simulated reality.
- **WP4 Control and real-time simulation of construction** that developed applications for better managing and controlling construction site activities using digital twin data.
- **WP5 Digital twin based structural monitoring and asset management** that established a real-time connection between physical infrastructures and virtual yet realistic numerical models of such assets for the purpose of supporting maintenance and asset management tasks.
- **WP6 Social innovation, and standardization** that determined future trajectories of ASHVIN developed innovations, including standardization triggering standards to be applied by the market in connection with the deployment of new innovative privacy focused practices within the industry.
- **WP7 Demonstration of digital twin methods** that demonstrated the developed ASHVIN digital twin toolkit across 10 demonstration sites.

The digital **ASHVIN system includes several technical layers** that enable end-users to collect data from construction sites or infrastructure asset sites, analyse and monitor the collected data, and visualise it through a dedicated digital twin platform. The system contributes to

better and more informed decision-making, risk anticipation, and damage detection across construction and maintenance projects.

The figure below shows that the ASHVIN platform integrates sensor devices and edge computing instances to collect data. This data is fed to the ASHVIN system via an Internet of Things platform (IoT) (created and managed by our partner, Mainflux), allowing connectivity, data management and sensor/edge computing device management. This platform is integrated with the game engine-based digital twin platform (developed by our partner, Digital Twin Technology) that allows 4D visualisation. In addition, the **ASHVIN toolkit¹**, composed of 10 digital smart building tools, runs on the Digital Twin platform, enabling it to monitor and assess different aspects of the project based on its needs.

Figure 1 Overview of the ASHVIN system

The ASHVIN system supports its target end-users (e.g., AEC sector project managers and workers) in the three different key phases, including:

- **Desing and engineering phase** enhancing the building planning process with evidence-based and predictive design models.
- **Construction phase** supporting notably the monitoring of operational and structural safety, and work progress at the construction site.

¹ <https://www.ashvin.eu/digital-toolkit/>

- **Maintenance phase** supporting notably early risk assessment and damage detection of infrastructure assets.

The next figure shows how the ten ASHVIN demonstration sites focused on these three phases; each site was dedicated to one specific project phase.

Figure 2 ASHVIN Demonstration Sites Targeting Different Phases

The ASHVIN digital twin toolkit aims to improve the work processes in the three phases. Furthermore, to monitor the impact of the developed digital twin tools, the partners defined a set of key performance indicators (KPI) that were monitored at the demonstration sites based on the deployed tool. The next figure links each ASHVIN tool with the set KPIs.

Figure 3 The ASHVIN Digital Twin Tools Linked to the Aimed Key Performance Indicators

Finally, the 10 tools composing the ASHVIN Digital Twin toolkit were deployed across the **demonstration sites**². The next table lists the ASHVIN Demonstration Sites and the tools that were piloted at each site.

#	Demo Site Name	
1.	Bridges for high-speed railways in Spain	
2.	Building Renovation in Poland	
3.	Airport runway in Croatia	
4.	Logistics hall construction in Germany	

² <https://www.ashvin.eu/demonstrators/>

5.	Kineum office building in Sweden	
6.	Office Buildings in Spain	
7.	Bridges in highway network in Spain	
8.	Footbridge in Germany	
9.	Sport stadium roof structure in Germany	
10.	Quay wall in the Netherlands	

Based on these demonstration sites and the digital twin tool pilots, we have drafted the set of the ASHVIN use cases following a specific methodology described in the next section.

1.2 ASHVIN Use Case Methodology

The ASHVIN use cases were drafted following the recommendations of **the BuildingSMART International use case database platform**³. BuildingSMART⁴ is an international organisation which aims to improve the exchange of information between software applications used in the construction industry. It has developed IFC as a neutral and open specification for BIM. currently, they focus on the development and active use of open internationally recognized standards, applications, training, and certification procedures. The goal is to achieve wider uptake of digital twin by the AEC industry, investors, building owners, and facility managers.

This process of documentation of the demonstration activities is based on ISO 29481-1: 2016 (Building information models — Information delivery manual) and it ensures a common language and a uniform understanding of BIM/digital twin applications (use cases) within the entire construction and real estate industry. Standardized use cases enable the capture and specification of exchange and actors involved in a unified manner, to ensure the implementation of best practices, which are accessible to all members within the built industry. In total within the ASHVIN project, 9 use cases were developed. Although Information Delivery Manual (IDM) standards are followed for use case definition, the ASHVIN use cases are tailored to include objectives of the use case as well as ASHVIN Project

³ <https://ucm.buildingsmart.org>

⁴ www.buildingsmart.org

objectives being validated upon demonstrating the use case on a project site.

Accordingly, a ASHVIN Use case contains four sections as detailed in the table below.

Table 1 ASHVIN Use Case Structure

Section title	Description of the section
Section 1: General definition of the use case	The first section gives an overview of the use-case description followed by the scope of the use case, benefits, limitations, comparison to conventional methods of the implementation of the use-case, and objective-based ASHVIN solution for the same.
Section 2: Overall Process across life cycle stages	The process of implementation of the use case is described using a process map based on Business Process Modelling Notation highlighting life cycle stage segregated processes, actors involved in the process, and exchange requirements for the entire process. The process is also described for life cycle stages based on ISO22263.
Section 3: Demonstration of implementation of Use cases	The process described in the previous section is demonstrated through a project site to provide an example of the implementation of the use case as well as validate the objectives of the use case based on results analysis from the implementation of the use case on the ASHVIN demonstration project.
Section 4: Exchange requirements	File format exchange requirements across life cycle stages and processes are highlighted and described in the last section.

3 ASHVIN USE CASES FOR DESIGN AND ENGINEERING

Three use cases focus on design and engineering phases of the construction projects. As shown in Figure 4, four tools of the ASHVIN digital twin toolkit can be deployed for this phase.

Figure 4 ASHVIN tools for Design and Engineering Phase

3.1 Embodied Carbon Footprint Analysis

This use case, entitled Embodied Carbon Footprint Analysis, is related to the **BRICS tool** (full name: Performance Indicator (PI) assessment of solutions in the design space) and is related to the **demo site #8 Footbridge in Dortmund, Germany**.

This use case presents the scoring performance indicator values related to carbon footprint calculation. It focuses on feedback a database with the embodied carbon footprint data from past and running construction projects. These data allow assessment of the performance of a structure, help to understand the sensitivity of the performance indicators with respect to design changes and support an objective data-based decision-making process in the early design phase.

Download the complete use case in open access: <https://zenodo.org/records/10907206>

3.2 Evidence Based Early Phase Design Recommendations Utilizing Knowledge Data Bases

This use case is related to the **EBD tool** (full name: Evidence Based design (EBD) support tool for recycling historic data as input at the early project stages) and related to the **demo site #8 Footbridge in Germany**.

This use case presents the evidence-based design helping the footbridge designer in the early design phases to get a broad overview of the design space. With this overview, the designer is enabled to make an informed decision on which type of design should be investigated in more detail. The insights are provided to the user in three distinct categories: predictions, warnings, and recommendations.

Download the complete use case in open access: <https://zenodo.org/records/10907231>

3.3 Generative Design Modeler

This use case is related to the **GEN tool** (full name: Generative design modeller to support design for productivity, resource efficiency and safety), and related to the **demo site # 8 Footbridge in Germany**.

This use cases presents applying historic data from past construction operations that were tracked with construction site digital twin technology to support future design activities. The use can propose to use historic data, identify performance metricsm and then use parametric modeling, generative design, optimization, and pareto-front-based decision-making to support help designers already in early design stages.

Download the complete use case in open access: <https://zenodo.org/records/10907251>

4 ASHVIN USE CASE MODELS FOR CONSTRUCTION

ASHVIN presents two use cases dedicated to the construction phase. Also, as shown in Figure 5, four tools from the ASHVIN Digital Twin toolkit can be used to support the work of the project managers in this phase.

Figure 5 ASHVIN tools for Construction Phase

4.1 Quality Control of Installed Building Elements during Construction using Onsite Digital Twin Data

This use case is related to the **CMT tool** (full name: A configuration management tool to track as-designed and as-built, as well as to allow for seamless commissioning), and related to the **demo site#5 Kineum Building in Gothenburg, Sweden.**

The use case presents a comprehensive overview and directions for utilizing the Configuration Management based framework to aid quality control in construction sites to achieve optimized productivity, resource efficiency, safety, and reduced costs, which are the key performance indicators of the projects. Configuration Management Use Case (CMT) was deployed on several demonstration projects within Europe for quality control of installed building elements during construction using onsite Digital Twin (DT) data. The use case significantly improved the resource efficiency, productivity, safety, and costs at construction sites under study.

Download the complete use case in open access: <https://zenodo.org/records/10907286>

4.2 Simulation of Activities for the Digital Twin of a Construction Area by Collecting Automated Data to Have Higher Efficiency

This use case is related to the **DES tool** (full name: Simulation-based real-time construction site and logistics planning tool) and related to the **demo site #4 Logistics Hall in Germany.**

This use case focuses on real-time discrete event simulation (DES) of processes during the construction phase. Real-time Discrete Event Simulation enables the simulation of construction site activities and the evaluation of their impacts on performance indicators (PIs) for productive, resource-efficient, and safe construction works. In close alignment with demonstration cases, work process patterns were determined to develop Discrete Event Simulation mechanism models. Discrete Event System Specification (DEVS) formalisms were created to build a basis for semantic understanding of each Discrete Event Simulation model. The discrete event simulation mechanisms can account for the site's supply-chain logistical, resource-dependent, and spatial characteristics and can use real-time Digital Twin data generated by sensors to predict future construction works.

Download the complete use case in open access: <https://zenodo.org/records/10907303>

5 ASHVIN USE CASE MODELS FOR MAINTENANCE

ASHVIN presents four use cases based on digital twin tools and models developed to support the maintenance of infrastructure assets. As shown in Figure 6, three tools from the ASHVIN digital twin toolkit are dedicated to this phase.

Figure 6 ASHVIN tools for Maintenance Phase

5.1 Risk-Based Status Assessment Use Case with Key Performance Indicators Dashboard

This use case is related to the **RISA tool** (full name: Risk-based status assessment tool with KPI dashboard), and to the **demo site #3 Airport runway in Croatia**.

This use case interactively reviews and utilises specific outputs of the risk assessment and the consequence modelling in risk analysis to choose the optimal maintenance scenario for the maintenance of the asset using asset management key performance indicators.

Download the complete use case in open access: <https://zenodo.org/records/10907437>

5.2 Digital Twin Enabled Multi Physics Simulation And Model Matching

This use case is related to the **MatchFem tool** (full name: Multi-physics model matching tool for status assessment of bridges and buildings), and to two **demo sites #1 Bridges for high-speed railways in Spain and #7 Bridges in highway network in Spain**.

Enabling meaningful simulations within new human-infrastructure interfaces such as Digital twins is paramount. Accessing the power of simulation opens manifold new ways for observation, understanding, analysis and prediction of numerous scenarios to which the asset may be faced. As a result, managers can access countless ways of acquiring synthetic

data to make better, more informed decisions eventually. This use case document is conceived as a fundamental part of this endeavour. This use case contextualises information between multi-physics simulations and vaster information constructs such as digital twins. 3D geometries, measurements, simulations, and asset management coexist in such information constructs.

Download the complete use case in open access: <https://zenodo.org/records/10907334>

5.3 GIS Integrator for Digital Twin Based Asset Management

This use case is related to the **GISI tool** (full name: GIS integrator for digital twin-based asset management), and to the **demo site #3 Airport runway in Croatia**.

This use case is dedicated to seamlessly integrating image data for condition assessment, categorization, and quantification of damages associated with infrastructure assets to effectively automate the process of damage detection and geolocation of the identified damage for better asset management.

Download the complete use case in open access: <https://zenodo.org/records/10907363>

5.4 Digital Twinning of Concrete Consolidation Quality Process

The proposed use case aims to facilitate real-time monitoring of concrete consolidation quality using digital twin data acquired from construction sites with the help of accelerometers to measure the formwork accelerations during the vibration of concrete. This monitoring supports the quality control team in achieving real-time quality assurance and developing real-time solutions for concrete placement and vibration workmanship, especially in the case of a construction site where casting is continuous.

The current monitoring practice relies on visual and time-consuming feedback by project managers, which can be subjective. Therefore, in the conventional method poor workmanship cannot be detected well on the spot; rather, the concrete is inspected and repaired after it becomes hardened. Hence, retroactive quality control to achieve real-time quality assurance of concrete is beneficial, which can be achieved through a monitoring and warning solution for concrete placement and vibration workmanship quality, especially in the case of a construction site where casting is continuous.

The ASHVIN system comprises [10 smart building applications](#), and this use case is related to a specific model developed by Digital Twin Technologies (DTT) and the Polytechnic University of Catalunya (UPC) for real-time monitoring of vibration quality to address concrete consolidation issues proactively.

The ASHVIN toolkit was demonstrated across [10 European demonstration sites](#), and this use case is related to the **demo site #6 Office building in Spain**.

Download the complete use case in open access: <https://zenodo.org/records/10907458>